

Mechanochemically designed bismuth-based halide perovskites for efficient photocatalytic oxidation of vanillyl alcohol

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Summary

Halide perovskite materials (HPM) have been recently employed as photocatalysts in H₂ generation, CO₂ reduction and organic synthesis. However, the high toxicity of lead is directing research to Pb-free halide perovskites with bismuth as main candidate to replace Pb. This contribution discloses the synthesis of two bismuth-based halide perovskites with chemical composition Cs₂AgBiBr₆ and Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ via a solvent-free mechanochemical process in a ball mill. The obtained perovskite powders were characterized via X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and absorption and photoluminescence (PL) steady-state and time-resolved spectroscopy. Cs₂AgBiBr₆ was able to absorb more into the visible region ($E_g = 2.12$ eV) as compared to Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ ($E_g = 2.53$ eV). Additionally, PL time decays were considerably longer for Cs₂AgBiBr₆ ($\tau_{av} = 740$ ns) with respect to Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ ($\tau_{av} = 0.3$ ns). Both photo-systems were employed in the oxidation of vanillyl alcohol to vanillin, the aldehyde derivative, under UV or visible illumination. Moderate values of photocatalytic conversion (15-30%) were observed except for Cs₂AgBiBr₆ under visible light irradiation where 95% conversion could be obtained after only 80 minutes of exposition. PL measurements with the fluorescent probe hydroethidine and electron spin resonance (ESR) demonstrated the formation of superoxide radical species ($\bullet\text{O}_2^-$) after photoexcitation, with a larger concentration observed for Cs₂AgBiBr₆ under visible light due to higher absorption and longer lifetime of the photogenerated charge carriers. Time-resolved PL measurements of both catalysts grinded with vanillyl alcohol powder showed light on the oxidation step upon irradiation taking place due to a hole transfer process from the valence band of the catalysts.

Introduction

Halide perovskite materials (HPM) have emerged as extremely efficient semiconductors in the field of photovoltaics due to their remarkable optoelectronic properties with high extinction coefficients, optimum band gaps, high photoluminescence quantum yields and long charge carrier diffusion lengths. Additionally, HPM have recently gained a considerable interest in photocatalysis with valuable results in H₂ generation, CO₂ reduction, pollutant degradation and organic synthesis.^{1,2} Thus, the excellent performance of HPM in photocatalysis has established a new paradigm in artificial photosynthesis paving the way for the discovery of related HPM photocatalysts.³⁻⁵

The ample majority of HPM photocatalysts employ divalent Pb²⁺ as B cation in the ABX₃ chemical formula with Cs, CH₃NH₃⁺ = MA or (NH₂)₂CH⁺ = FA as monovalent A cation and Br⁻ or I⁻ as halide.⁶ The solar-to-chemical fuel conversion using HPM is performed in aqueous HI for the water splitting while ethyl acetate with a trace amount of water is normally employed in photocatalytic CO₂ reduction.⁶ However, the high rate of degradation against the environmental factors including moisture of Pb-based HPM imposes severe limitations for further improvements of this type of applications. Pb-based HPM have been also employed in photocatalytic organic reactions including chemical transformations and photopolymerization.⁶⁻¹⁰ The absence of water traces in the involved reactions guarantees the long-term stability of HPM for different reaction cycles.⁴ In recent reports, lead-free multidimensional halide perovskites have been utilized to eliminate the toxic lead element in the HPM, for instance in ring-opening reaction of epoxides or in the C(sp³)-H bond activation of toluene.^{11,12} However, there is still a large room for the utilization of Pb-free HPMS in the photocatalysis of organic reactions.¹³⁻¹⁶

Herein we have explored mechanochemically designed bismuth-based halide perovskites, namely Cs₂AgBiBr₆ and Cs₃Bi₂Br₉, in the photocatalytic oxidation of vanillyl alcohol to vanillin as model reaction. Vanillin is one of the most relevant and well-known flavoring molecules, with applications in various sectors, including alimentary, cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries. Currently, vanillin is typically produced at industrial scale from petro-based feedstocks such as

glyoxylic acid and guaiacol, through non-environmentally friendly protocols such as the Riedel process. Therefore, preparation of vanillin through a photocatalytic approach employing lignin derived-compounds, like vanillyl alcohol, is a highly promising opportunity. Both photocatalysts were synthesized via solid state mechanochemistry (without the use of any solvent) obtaining high purity compounds. The conversion for the photocatalytic reaction varies largely with the catalyst and the employed range of the light. An almost 100% conversion could be obtained with $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ double perovskite under visible illumination after only 80 minutes exposure while the conversion was reduced to 30% for $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ even under UV illumination. Stability tests of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ photocatalysts demonstrated an excellent performance after several reaction cycles which potentially validates the use of this catalyst in commercial applications.

Results and discussion

Catalyst Characterization

Bi-based photocatalysts were synthesized by using a solid state (no solvent) mechanochemical approach from their precursors under ambient atmosphere (Figure S1). The use of ball milling for the synthesis of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ perovskites is an environmentally friendly approach that may pave the way for the discovery of further applications of these materials.^{11,17,18} Further details on the synthetic protocol can be found in the Supporting Information. Figure 1 displays X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements for both photocatalysts, $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$, together with simulated diffractograms obtained from crystallography databases. The position and relative intensity of the Bragg reflections in the experimental diffractograms perfectly match simulated ones for both materials, which confirms the successful synthesis of the expected Bi-based perovskites. The absence of any other additional reflection peak dismisses incomplete reactions of the precursors or the formation of side products which might have a detrimental impact on the structure of the perovskite (or the photocatalytic oxidation). Figure S5 includes the XRD patterns of all chemical precursors employed in the synthesis of both photocatalysts. It can be clearly seen that the XRD peaks from the precursors are not visible in the diffractogram of the synthesized powder which excludes the presence of precursors in the obtained perovskites. Moreover, the small width of XRD peaks together with their

high signal-to-noise ratio indicated the high crystallinity of the powders with no amorphous phases. The structure of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ double perovskite consists of a tridimensional (3D) network of alternate AgBr_6 or BiBr_6 octahedra sharing all corners with Cs cations incorporated into the octahedral voids to balance the charge.^{19–21} On the contrary, $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ is isostructural to 3D CsPbBr_3 but adopting a vacancy-ordered perovskite structure with only two-thirds of the B cation position occupied by bismuth and the one-third unoccupied site in octahedra remains vacant.^{22–24}

The morphology of synthesized Bi-based perovskites was studied using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Figure S2 displays SEM images of both photocatalysts at different magnifications showing particles with a wide variety of dimensions but always within the micrometer size range. No significant difference in the size of both perovskite particles was observed, which exclude this argument to account for a potential variation in catalytic performance between both photocatalysts. Among synthesized particles, very smooth surfaces were observed in some of them, which is a typical feature of ball milling prepared halide perovskites.²⁵ Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis was also performed to evaluate the elemental composition of the powders. Figures S3 and S4 indicated the homogeneous distribution of Cs, Ag, Bi and Br atoms in $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ while Cs, Bi and Br elements were also regularly distributed in SEM images of $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$.

Figure 1. Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ (A) and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ (B) Bi-based perovskites obtained from ball milling. Simulated XRD diffractograms are also shown for comparison.

The absorption ability of both materials was determined by using UV-visible diffuse reflection spectroscopy. Figure 2A shows the Kubelka-Munk spectra with an intense absorption in the blue side of the visible region for both powders. In the UV region (data not shown), the signal is saturated which indicates a strong absorption. $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ displays an additional broad absorption band centered at 500 nm which revealed a larger formation of charge carriers under visible light illumination with respect to $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$. The different absorption ability under visible light is expected to significantly influence photocatalytic activity variations between both perovskites. The energy of the bandgap was calculated using the Tauc plot obtaining values of 2.12 eV and 2.53 eV for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ perovskites, respectively. The larger bandgap of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ is attributed to its 3D structure compared to the layered vacancy-ordered $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ material.

Figure 2. A) Kubelka–Munk spectra obtained from diffuse reflectance measurements of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ (black solid line) and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ (red solid line). (B) Tauc plot of both compounds showing an indirect band gap of 2.12 eV and 2.53 eV for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ perovskites, respectively. Time-resolved

photoluminescence decays of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ (C) and Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ (D) perovskites. λ_{exc} = 405 nm.

To investigate the excited state dynamics of both catalysts after illumination, steady-state and time-resolved photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy was performed. Figure S6 shows PL spectra for both catalysts after excitation at 400 nm. The obtained PL signals match well with those previously reported in literature, a broad PL band centered around 575 nm for Cs₂AgBiBr₆ and a narrow PL peak at 470 nm with a shoulder in the red region for Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ powder.^{20,26} PL decays were also measured at the maxima of PL signal after excitation at 405 nm with a picosecond pulsed laser (Figure 2C and 2D). The time range of the observed PL decay is on the pico- to nanosecond scale for Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ while it is on the nano- to microsecond regime for Cs₂AgBiBr₆. In particular, a bi-exponential function was used to fit the experimental data, finding an average time constant of 0.3 and 740 ns for Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ and Cs₂AgBiBr₆ perovskites, respectively. The long time constant can be ascribed to band-to-band radiative recombination of free charges via indirect bandgap nature of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ perovskite while the short component in Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ powder is attributed to charge transfer from excited states to trap states.^{20,26–28} The longer dynamics of photogenerated charges in Cs₂AgBiBr₆ are expected to generate a larger photocatalytic conversion due to the higher probability for reaction with the reagent.

Photocatalytic oxidation of vanillyl alcohol

Scheme S1 displays the chemical reaction that will be intended to be catalyzed with the previously synthesized Pb-free perovskites. Indeed, the main advantage of the employed Bi-based photocatalysts is the removal of the toxic Pb from the structure of the perovskite. The photocatalytic activity of both Bi-based catalysts was separately evaluated under visible light and UV irradiation in the oxidative reaction of vanillyl alcohol in a polar solvent (acetonitrile) in the presence of molecular oxygen to generate the aldehyde derivative, vanillin. Figure 3 displays the performance of both catalysts under visible (Fig. 3A) and UV (Fig. 3B) light at different reaction times (0-140 minutes; every 20 minutes). The reaction vessel was not illuminated during the initial 20 minutes which results in a conversion

practically negligible (close to zero). In the longer reaction times (upon illumination), a gradual increase in conversion is determined as a result of the photocatalytic oxidation. The conversion values are higher upon visible light illumination or employing $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ as photocatalyst with respect to UV light or using $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$, respectively. Conversion of 95% and 50% upon visible illumination or 50% and 15% upon UV light exposition were obtained after 140 minutes for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ photocatalysts, respectively. The higher conversion of the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ catalyst compared to the $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ one under visible illumination can be explained due to its lower bandgap which pumps more photogenerated charges into the conduction band. Regarding UV illumination, the higher conversion observed for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ catalyst cannot be ascribed to a larger absorption capacity and should be explained due to different intrinsic properties of each catalyst.

Figure 3C displays the conversion and selectivity of the photocatalytic oxidation of vanillyl alcohol to vanillin after 80 minutes of visible or UV illumination for each Bi-based catalyst. The conversion is practically quantitative (~95%) for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ under visible light irradiation while it drops to a range of 10-40% for UV light exposition for $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$. Regarding the selectivity, similar values (30-40%) could be observed for both photocatalysts and illumination conditions, which may indicate similar reaction mechanism in all cases. The high vanillyl alcohol conversion when using $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ catalyst under visible illumination is remarkable as compared to literature reported 3D perovskites (even containing Pb). For example, CsPbBr_3 (5 mg/ml concentration) reached a low conversion of ~3% for the photocatalytic oxidation of benzyl alcohol while the hybrid, $(\text{HC}(\text{NH}_2):\text{FA})$, FAPbBr_3 perovskite (4 mg/ml concentration) could only provide a 15% conversion for the oxidation of benzylic alcohol after 8-20 h under visible light irradiation, respectively.

The stability of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ under visible light illumination was subsequently tested at different reaction cycles. Figure 3D displays similar values of conversion (~95%) for a total of four cycles with no loss of selectivity among the different cycles. To monitor the stability of the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ photocatalyst after every cycle,

XRD measurements of the recovered $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ powder were carried out. Figure S8 displays the XRD patterns of the powders after the photoreactions together with those of the simulated and as-prepared $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ powder. The XRD signals at 13.9° , 15.7° , 22.3° , 26.2° , 27.4° , 31.8° , 35.7° and 39.2° due to the structure of the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ perovskite are clearly preserved with similar relative intensity and FWHM throughout all patterns, which guarantees that the crystal structure of the photocatalyst was fully retained after every photocatalytic cycle. The minor XRD signal centered around 31° is the only mismatch among all patterns, which might be originated due to the AgBr precursor (Figure S5). This signal would imply a slow decomposition of the photocatalyst after the reactions. The previous light results demonstrate the high conversion and relatively high stability of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ in the visible light photo-oxidative conversion of vanillyl alcohol.

Figure 3. Vanillyl alcohol conversion using $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ (red squares) and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ (green squares) as photocatalysts at different reaction times upon visible (A) and UV light irradiation (B). Photocatalytic conversion and selectivity of vanillyl alcohol to vanillin after 80 minutes of visible or UV illumination (C). Reusability test for the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ catalyst under visible illumination (D). UV light

covers illumination from 250-400 nm. Visible light includes the 400-750 nm region. Light intensity is 100 mW/cm².

Reaction Mechanism

To get additional insights into the mechanism involved in the photocatalytic oxidation of vanillyl alcohol, several experiments were subsequently performed. The formation of superoxide radicals ($\bullet\text{O}_2^-$) after photoexcitation of the catalyst is generally reported to initiate oxidative catalytic reactions.^{6,7} Thus, to investigate the presence of $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ due to the reaction of O_2 with photoexcited electrons in the conduction band of the catalyst, a molecular fluorescent probe, hydroethidine (HE), was employed.²⁹ The ground state of HE is known to react with $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radical species to generate highly fluorescence ethidium compounds with maximum wavelength at 610 nm.²⁹ $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ photocatalysts were dispersed in acetonitrile solutions containing the HE fluorescent probe (0.05 mM). Figure 4 displays PL spectra for both photocatalysts at different irradiation times under visible light irradiation. The fluorescent signal at 610 nm was very weak in the absence of light irradiation, while the typical broad emission band centered at 610 nm was observed upon illumination. The height of PL signal increases at longer light exposition for both photocatalysts indicating the gradual reaction of HE with molecular oxygen. This result demonstrates the ability of both photocatalysts to generate $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radicals which has been reported to trigger the photocatalytic oxidation of several alcohols.^{1,6} However, the rate of PL signal increase is larger in $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ as compared to $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ (Figure 4C), indicating a larger concentration of $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radicals for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ as photocatalyst. The higher vanillyl alcohol conversion observed in photoreactions promoted by $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ can be partially explained due to its larger ability to generate $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radicals.

Figure 4. PL signal of a hydroethidine solution in acetonitrile in the presence of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ (A) or Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ (B) photocatalysts upon different illumination times. (C) Variation of PL signal at the maximum of the peak for Cs₂AgBiBr₆ (blue line) and Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ (red line) photocatalysts at different irradiation times with visible light.

To further validate the mechanism of photocatalytic oxidation of vanillyl alcohol, electron spin resonance (ESR) spectroscopy was performed on a suspension of the photocatalyst in the presence of 5,5-dimethyl-pyrroline *N*-oxide (DMPO) that acts as a scavenger of superoxide radicals ($\bullet\text{O}_2^-$). Figure 5 displays the ESR signals for each photocatalyst in the dark and under 20 minutes of visible light irradiation. In the absence of illumination, ESR signals for both catalysts are negligible, reflecting the limited formation of $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radicals. Upon excitation with visible light, the three typical components of the DMPO- $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ adducts can be detected in the Cs₂AgBiBr₆ and Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ promoted photoreaction which demonstrates that photogenerated electrons are capable of reducing O₂ to $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radicals. Besides, the ESR signals for Cs₃Bi₂Br₉ are less intense, which indicates a reduced photogenerated concentration of $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radicals with respect to Cs₂AgBiBr₆. Both PL measurements with hydroethidine and ESR experiments revealed the high capacity of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ to generate a high concentration of $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radicals under visible light irradiation. In view of the results obtained in the characterization section, the superior $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radical formation could be attributed to the intense absorption in the visible light region and the longer lifetime of the photogenerated charges.

Figure 5. DMPO-trapped superoxide radical ESR spectra of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ (blue line) and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ (red line) dispersed in acetonitrile under visible illumination. ESR spectra in dark are also shown for comparison.

In the reported literature, photogenerated holes in the valence band of the perovskite are assumed to oxidize alcohols to a carbocation that eventually reacts with $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ radicals to generate the final aldehyde product.^{6,7} In general, the driving force for alcohol oxidation (by the generated hole) is controlled by the energy level of the valence band and the oxidation potential of the alcohol. For the perovskites employed in this work, values of +1.45 eV and +2.45 vs. NHE were measured for the energy of the valence band maximum for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$, respectively.³⁰ Regarding the oxidation potential of the vanillyl alcohol, a value of approximately +0.9 eV vs. NHE reference electrode has been reported,²⁵ which ensures the thermodynamic feasibility of the reaction (Figure 6). However, reaction kinetics also play a key role in the hole transfer process governing the dynamics of the photocatalytic process.

Figure 6. Energy level diagram for valence and conduction band of both $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ photocatalysts and oxidation potential of vanillyl alcohol.

Figure 7A and 7B display PL time decays of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ and $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ perovskites in the presence and in the absence of vanillyl alcohol. Time-resolved measurements were performed by mixing the two powders with a mortar. Interestingly, PL signals are slower in the samples containing the alcohol, especially in $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$, indicating the effect of vanillyl alcohol on the deactivation of the perovskites. Thus, the presence of the alcohol slows down the radiative recombination rate of the electron/hole due to the transfer of the photogenerated hole to the alcohol to generate a radical carbocation. This process is apparently more intense in the $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ with respect to the $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ catalyst, which supports the observed higher photocatalytic conversion in $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ as compared to $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$.

Figure 7. PL time decays of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ (A) or $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ (B) photocatalysts with (green lines) and without (blue and red lines) the presence of vanillyl alcohol. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 405 \text{ nm}$

Conclusions

The design of mechanochemically synthesized $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ or $\text{Cs}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{Br}_9$ perovskites as effective and highly stable photocatalysts in the oxidation reaction of vanillyl alcohol has been successfully accomplished. The high photocatalytic conversion (95%) of $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ under visible illumination could be attributed to the larger absorption in the visible light region and longer lifetime of photogenerated electrons and holes. Optoelectronic properties of the catalysts were found to be correlated to the conversion of the reaction, obtaining a structure-property-performance relationship. Investigations on the reaction mechanism revealed that photogenerated electrons react with O_2 to generate superoxide radicals $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ and holes mediate in the oxidation of vanillyl alcohol. Although both processes are present in both photocatalysts, demonstrating the same reaction mechanism in both cases, the stronger signals observed for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ under visible light irradiation account for its enhanced photocatalytic conversion. Bismuth-based halide perovskites are demonstrated to be not only competitive as photocatalysts in organic synthesis (similarly to the lead halide perovskites) but able to circumvent the inherent toxicity and poor stability of Pb-based systems.

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